

DataAge: Age of Information in SWIPT-Driven Short Packet IoT Wireless Communications

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Abstract—Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) enabled wireless cooperative communication system is an emerging technology for future wireless communication applications. Furthermore, the Internet of Things (IoT) serves a diverse range of purposes, some of which are mission-critical and require constantly evolving real-time data. Thus, the information received at the destination must be updated timely manner to ensure its freshness. A performance metric named age of information (AoI) has been introduced to measure the freshness of received information. This study estimates the AoI of a SWIPT assisted decode and forward two-way relay assisted status update system in which two sources attempt to exchange status updates as quickly as possible to the destination. The relay system employs short packet communication to adhere to the latency and reliability requirements of the wireless communication system. We study the average Age of Information (AAoI) at the destination in the proposed relay network and derive approximations for the weighted sum AAoI under two different types of transmission scheduling policies at the relay: *transmit without waiting (TWW)* and *wait until charged (WUC)*. Furthermore, the effects of transmission power, packet size, the distance between relay and sources and block-length on the weighted sum AAoI of the proposed SWIPT assisted short packet relay network are extensively investigated. The performance differences of the considered transmission policies are compared and insights are provided. Numerical simulations using the Monte Carlo method have been employed to validate derived analytical expressions.

Index Terms—Age of information, finite block-length analysis, short-packet communication, simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) and ultra-reliable low-latency communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

The internet of things (IoT), cyber-physical systems, and robotic networks provide enormous opportunities to use technology to improve our daily lives [2]–[4]. Data-gathering de-

vices of these communication networks acquire large amounts of data at once. Thus, a large number of data chunks are communicated within wireless networks over a considered amount of time period, which allows communication between multiple nodes such as sensors, actuators, machines, autonomous vehicles, drones, and a variety of other smart devices (things). Only having low-latency data transmission is insufficient for dealing with time-critical information in these applications and it is also necessary to ensure the freshness of the received data [5]. To measure the freshness of the time-critical information, researchers have focused their attention on the new performance metric named age of information (AoI) [1], [5], [6].

The AoI evaluates information freshness from the perspective of the destination [7], as an alternative to the well-established performance metrics such as packet delay, round-trip latency, etc. The AoI measures the time interval between the generation and delivery of the most recently delivered packet, while packet delay measures the time interval between packet creation and delivery [8]. Furthermore, as a timeliness metric, the AoI outperforms delay in effectively capturing the freshness of updates. For instance, even when the transmission delay is minimal, received data may not always be considered fresh if the packet generation rate is low. Conversely, if the update generation rate is high, the received data may still lack freshness if packets experience substantial queuing delays during transmission. Therefore, AoI is recognized as a valuable and pivotal performance metric for mission-critical IoT applications [9]. One of the primary goals for future wireless communication networks is to establish reliable and low-latency connections for transmitting small data packets. However, designing an optimal wireless communication system that fulfills these requirements remains a significant challenge. On the other hand, short-packet communication plays a crucial role in 5G and beyond 5G networks by using finite block-length codewords for data transmissions. This characteristic distinguishes future wireless networks from traditional ones, which primarily rely on lengthy packet communication with infinite block-length codewords [10], [11]. Moreover, the present physical-layer system designs heavily depend on classical information-theory analysis guidelines, which are no longer applicable in the case of short-packet transmission [11]–[14]. In other words, it is impractical to design future mission-critical wireless networks using existing theoretical results based on an asymptotic block-length assumption. To address this issue, Polyanskiy, Poor, and Verdú (PPV) [15] derived an accurate approximation of the achievable coding

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rate for additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channels within the finite block-length regime. Existing literature has been expanded to investigate the coding rate in the finite block-length regime under various situations, such as over block-fading [16], MIMO [17], relaying [18] and multi-access communication [19].

Moreover, simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) is a key enabling technology for future wireless communication systems to improve spectral efficiency. In addition, the SWIPT has received significant attention from researchers as a potential solution to address the energy constraint problem of wireless devices in IoT networks. The SWIPT enables the simultaneous transmission of both data and energy with the support of RF signals while providing an essential solution for the rapid drainage of batteries in wireless devices. Due to these sophisticated characteristics of the SWIPT, many studies have begun to examine the use of SWIPT for wireless IoT relay devices with limited battery capacity and that need external charging to maintain network connectivity [20]–[23]. Furthermore, SWIPT enabled two-way communication systems were investigated in [22], [24], [25]. In the real world, these types of SWIPT enabled two-way relays can be employed as roadside units in vehicular communication networks and as UAV relays in UAV-assisted wireless networks. However, the incorporation of energy harvesting into wireless networks introduces additional complexity [26], [27]. In shared environments, devices contend for both data transmission and energy harvesting opportunities. This heightened competition can give rise to conflicts over resource allocation, consequently affecting the reliability and timeliness of information [28], [29]. Fluctuations in energy availability for devices relying on harvesting further exacerbate the issue, potentially resulting in increased data packet loss and diminished overall communication reliability [1]. Prioritizing energy harvesting over immediate information transmission introduces trade-offs, which may lead to delays. The storage of data until sufficient energy is harvested can also vie for limited buffer space, causing further delays, potentially impacting the freshness of information. Thus, SWIPT enabled cooperative communication systems should be investigated by integrating finite block-length information theory and AoI to analyze how resource sharing will affect information freshness and reliability. However, the AoI analysis for energy harvesting relay networks is relatively novel. Most of the existing research was conducted on simple one-way relay networks or long-block-length transmission [30]–[33]. Thus, in sharp contrast to the existing works, this paper analyses the freshness of the information of a SWIPT and short packet communication assisted two-way relay system using finite block-length information theory and AoI to overcome the aforementioned drawbacks in existing works.

A. Related work

Few studies have investigated the timeliness of SWIPT systems using conventional timeliness metrics. For example, in [34], the authors discussed a latency-aware multi-antenna SWIPT system with battery-constrained receivers. In their

work, the authors jointly considered the interdependence of latency and battery dynamics in SWIPT-enabled systems. They proposed radio resource allocation schemes that enable the system to meet latency and energy harvesting (EH) requirements at the user equipment while preventing excessive battery depletion. However, these works on SWIPT have mainly focused on improving energy efficiency and latency, with less emphasis on the freshness and reliability of the information.

The AoI has been widely used as a performance metric to quantify the freshness of information over time. In recent times, few attempts have been made to apply AoI as a performance metric in SWIPT enabled wireless communication systems. In [29], the performance of the AoI is examined in a SWIPT enabled cooperative wireless communication system. The authors have calculated the AoI performance of the relay node for both SWIPT protocols: time-switching (TS) and power-switching (PS). However, it is important to note that in [29] authors did not pay significant attention to transmission errors and the specific policies employed for packet transmission. In contrast, our work places a strong emphasis on the block error rate, incorporating finite block length information theory to calculate transmission errors. Furthermore, we investigate various transmission policies to identify the optimal strategy for minimizing the AoI.

In [35], the AoI was employed to measure the freshness of the information in a SWIPT-enabled re-configurable intelligent surface (RIS) assisted communication network. The authors of [36] discussed the AoI as a performance metric for a sensor network equipped with wireless power transfer (WPT). However, both of these works have given little attention to the reliability of the transmissions and the transmission policies that are considered to reduce AoI. In addition, the authors of [37] investigated information freshness in a SWIPT enabled real-time monitoring system where several source nodes are responsible for delivering update packets to a single destination node. This work further examined the optimal online sampling policy for the proposed system configuration, aiming to minimize the average weighted sum of AoI values for various physical processes at the destination node. However, the vast majority of the existing literature related to the AoI and SWIPT regards asymptotic, in terms of block-length, analysis. On the other hand, Ref. [38]–[40] analyzed the performance of SWIPT-enabled energy harvesting cooperative communication systems using finite block-length information theory. However, these existing works related to finite block-length information theory and SWIPT also do not analyse the freshness of the information using AoI. Alternatively, simple communication scenarios were considered in these works. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, there are no works in the literature that analyze the information freshness of SWIPT-based cooperative wireless networks using finite block-length information theory and AoI, even though short packet communication is used in these networks to maintain latency and freshness of the information. To the best of the author's knowledge, this is the first study to analyze the freshness of information in a SWIPT-enabled communication network that employs short-packet communication. Furthermore, this is the first study to theoretically analyze the freshness of information in a SWIPT-

enabled relay under different types of transmission policies at the relay.

B. Motivation and Contribution

Motivated by the features of SWIPT, short packet communication and cooperative communication, as well as the need for assessing the timeliness of information in modern mission-critical applications, this work analyses the AoI in a SWIPT-enabled wireless cooperative short packet relay system, utilising finite block length information theory and AoI metrics. In summary, this work makes the following contributions.

- First, a theoretical model has been developed to measure the freshness of the information in a SWIPT-enabled short packet communication two-way cooperative relay scheme under the two type transmission policies at the relay named “*transmit without waiting (TWW)*” and “*wait until charged (WUC)*”.
- Secondly, expressions were presented for the block error rate (BLER) under each transmission policy separately, using different mathematical approximations. Based on the derived expressions, the BLER performance of the considered system is compared. Several key observations related to the impact of transmission power on the BLER are obtained.
- Thirdly, approximations for the AAoI of the proposed two-way relay scheme under the finite block-length constraint are derived for both transmission policies. Additionally, the accuracy of these approximations has been verified using Monte Carlo (MC) method-based numerical simulations.
- Finally, we analyze how the information freshness of the relay system varies when the transmission scheduling policy at the relay is altered across different transmission power levels. Additionally, we examine the effects of several factors, including block length, Rician factor, and packet size, on the weighted sum AAoI. MC-based numerical simulations are provided to verify the accuracy of the theoretical analysis.

C. Organization

The rest of the paper is arranged as follows: Section II presents the system model and the underlying assumptions and evaluates the reliability of the system and freshness of the information at the destination under proposed transmission policies using finite block-length analysis and the AoI analysis, respectively. We compare the proposed policies in Section III using extensive simulation results. Section IV concludes the paper. Several proofs have been added to the appendix to improve readability.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

As depicted in Fig. 1, this paper considers a two-way cooperative status update system where two source nodes, source A (S_A) and source B (S_B) exchange status updates with each other as timely as possible with the help of a bidirectional IoT relay node R (R). The sources in this system

are regarded as energy providers and the relay is equipped with an energy harvesting device and is capable of information transmission and harvesting energy simultaneously. The R adopts the dynamic power splitting technique [20]. In this paper, two types of transmissions and EH policies at R are considered : TWW and WUC .

- TWW : As shown in Fig. 1, we consider a two-time slot transmission scheme in which S_i sends updates to the R while harvesting energy during the first transmission time slot (T_1) and then the R exchange updates received from S_i using harvested energy during the second transmission time slot (T_2). The T_1 and T_2 are constant time slots and $S_i, i \in (A, B)$ transmits status updates which can be generated at the beginning of any time circle following generate-at-will updates generation model [41]. Under this policy, the relay uses energy harvested within the first transmission time slot for the transmission in the second transmission time slot without waiting. Suppose the harvested energy is less than the minimum required energy for the transmission. In that case, the relay does not transmit the received updates and updates received from both sources are destroyed at the relay. Also, if the update transmission is unsuccessful at the relay or destination nodes within the considered time circle, it is destroyed to keep the information fresh [42].
- WUC : Under the WUC policy, $S_i, i \in (A, B)$ generate status updates at the beginning of each transmission circle following generate-at-will updates generation model and then updates are transmitted to the R while R harvesting energy from the sources. However, suppose R is unable to harvest the required energy set by the system within the first time slot. In that case, it waits for the transmission until it harvests the required energy for an update exchange and after it harvests the required energy defined by the system, the R exchange latest updates in the second transmission slot (T_2). In this event, $S_i, i \in (A, B)$ sent an update at each transmission slot until R harvested the required power and the R transmits the most recent update received from the sources. Simply, relay will transmit the update received in the final time slot of the waiting time (T_w) to maintain the freshness of the information.

In addition, the following set of assumptions is taken into account throughout this paper:

- 1) There is no direct link between the source and the destination (opposite source) node due to intense shadowing or blockage. Therefore, the intermediate relay facilitates the transmission of messages from the source to the destination (opposite source). This system model considers a single relay node for simplicity.
- 2) The relay node employs the decode-and-forward (DF) technique as its relaying protocol.
- 3) The channel gains of each channel in this system are modeled using quasi-static block-fading and non-selective frequency parameters. The channel is independent and identically distributed from one block to the next. All wireless channels are modelled as Rayleigh

Fig. 1. (a) In the system model, sources A (S_A) and B (S_B) exchange status updates with each other with the help of a single relay (R); sources send updates to the R during the first transmission time slot T_1 while the R is harvesting energy and then the R exchanges updates received from each source using harvested energy during the second transmission time slot T_2 . (b) Timing diagram of the proposed cooperative strategies.

fading channels or Rician fading channels and stay constant during each transmission block.

- 4) The processing power required by the transmit/receive circuitry at the relay is insignificant as compared to the power utilized for signal transmission from the relay to the destination (opposite source) [22].
- 5) The up-link transmission between the source and the relay are performed in an orthogonal channel.

To facilitate a clear exposition, this paper concentrates on single-antenna transmission and frequency-flat fading channels. It is worth noting, however, that an extension of the system model to scenarios involving multiple antennas or frequency-selective fading is entirely feasible.

Throughout the paper, H_{ij} represents the channel coefficient of the channel between node i to node j where $i, j \in \{A, B, R\}$ and $i \neq j$. The small scale channel gain is $g_{ij} = |h_{ij}|^2$, where $h_{ij} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ is the fading channel coefficient. The probability density function (PDF) of the small-scale channel gain for the Rayleigh fading can be defined as $f_{g_{ij}}(z) = e^{-z}$, $z \geq 0$. In addition, the PDF of the g_{ij} for the Rician fading channel gain follows a non-central chi-square distribution and it can be expressed as:

$$f_{g_{ij}}(z) = \frac{(K_f + 1)e^{-K_f}}{\bar{g}} e^{-\frac{(K_f + 1)z}{\bar{g}}} I_0 \left(2\sqrt{\frac{K_f(K_f + 1)z}{\bar{g}}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $z \geq 0$, $\bar{g} = 1$, $I_0(\cdot)$ is the zero-order modified Bessel function of the first kind, and K_f is the Rician factor. The large scale channel gain α_{ij} is given by [18],

$$-10 \log_{10}(\alpha_{ij}) = 20 \log_{10}(d_{ij}) + 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi f_c}{c} \right), \quad (2)$$

where f_c , d_{ij} are the carrier frequency and distance between node i and node j respectively. c is the speed of light in the space. Thus the channel coefficient can be written as $H_{ij} = \sqrt{\alpha_{ij} g_{ij}}$ and channel gain is written as $G_{ij} = \alpha_{ij} g_{ij}$.

A. Block error analysis under finite block-length

The AoI is usually recognised as a destination-centric statistic since it measures the time difference between the present time and the generation time of the most recent update received by the destination. It only examines packets that are successfully received and forwarded to the destination. Furthermore, the AoI is greatly influenced by the transmission error rate and the update generation rate at the source. Then, our first objective is to study BLER at each destination (opposite source) in this system. The BLER at the destination under both transmission policies has been derived using different mathematical approximation techniques in this section.

1) *Transmission Policy 01 : TWW*: To calculate BLER at each node, it is necessary to derive the SNR at each node. The received SNR at the relay from each source node $S_{i'}$, $i' \in \{A, B\}$ is given by,

$$\gamma_R^{i'} = \frac{(1-\rho)P_{i'}G_{i'R}}{\sigma_R^2}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the power spitting factor, noise power at the relay is denoted as σ_R^2 and transmit power at the $S_{i'}$ given by $P_{i'}$. However, harvested amount of energy at R depends on the energy harvesting policy. Thus, we have analyzed the system model according to the considered energy harvesting policy at the R . Under the TWW policy, the energy harvested by the relay from each node is given by,

$$E_R^{i'} = \rho\eta P_{i'}G_{i'R}T_1, \quad (4)$$

where η is the energy conversion efficiency and T_1 is the transmission time of the first transmission slot and it can be calculated as $T_1 = n_R^{i'}T_s$, where $n_R^{i'}$ is the allocated block-length for the transmission between i' and R and T_s is the

symbol duration. Then, the total energy harvested by the relay within the first transmission slot is given by

$$E_R = \sum_{i'=\{A,B\}} E_{R'}^{i'} = \rho\eta T_1 (P_A G_{AR} + P_B G_{BR}). \quad (5)$$

The available energy harvested by the relay for transmission is given by

$$E_R^T = \begin{cases} E_{max}, & E_R \geq E_{max}, \\ E_R, & E_{max} > E_R > E_{min}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where E_{max} is the maximum energy limit that the relay can harvest and E_{min} is the minimum energy required for transmission. E_{min} can be calculated as $E_{min} = P_{min} T_2$, where P_{min} is the minimum required power for the transmission while T_2 is the time of the second transmission slot. T_2 is calculated as

$$T_2 = \sum_{i=\{A,B\}} n_i^R T_s, \quad (7)$$

where n_i^R is the allocated block-length for the transmission between R and i . Then, the transmit power of relay is calculated as $P_R = \frac{E_R^T}{T_2}$. During the second time slot, the received SNR at each $S_i \in \{A, B\}$ is given by

$$\gamma_i = \frac{P_R G_{Ri}}{\sigma_i^2}. \quad (8)$$

Then, using (5) and (6) SNR at the destination is expressed as

$$\gamma_i = \begin{cases} \frac{E_{max} \alpha_{Ri} G_{Ri}}{T_2 \sigma_i^2}, & E_R > E_{max} \\ \frac{E_R \alpha_{Ri} G_{Ri}}{T_2 \sigma_i^2}, & E_{max} \geq E_R \geq E_{min} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

An outage happens when the relay or opposite source is unable to decode the received message successfully. Hence, the system overall transmission error probability ε_i at each source node i can be calculated as

$$\varepsilon_i = \varepsilon_i^{i'} + (1 - \varepsilon_i^{i'}) \varepsilon_i^R, \quad (10)$$

where $i \neq i', i, i' \in \{A, B\}$ and ε_j^t is the decoding error probability at receiving node $j \in (i, R)$ for block received from node $t \in (i', R)$. Following Polyanskiy's results on short packet communication [15] and assuming that the receiver has the perfect channel state information, the expectation of the block error probability at the receiving node for a given block-length n_j^t can be written as

$$\varepsilon_j^t = \mathbb{E} \left[Q \left(\frac{n_j^t C(\gamma_j^t) - k_j^t}{\sqrt{n_j^t V(\gamma_j^t)}} \right) \right], \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ is the expectation operator, $Q(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_x^\infty e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}} dt$ and $V(\gamma_j^t)$ is the channel dispersion, which can be written $V(\gamma_j^t) = \frac{\log_2^2 e}{2} (1 - \frac{1}{(1+\gamma_j^t)^2})$. The variable $C(\gamma_j^t)$ denotes the channel capacity of a complex AWGN channel and it is given by $C(\gamma_j^t) = \log_2(1 + \gamma_j^t)$. The number of bits per block represents is by k_j^t . Moreover, under

the Rayleigh fading channel conditions, ε_j^t can be formulated as

$$\varepsilon_j^t = \int_0^\infty f_{\gamma_j^t}(z) Q \left(\frac{n_j^t C(\gamma_j^t) - k_j^t}{\sqrt{n_j^t V(\gamma_j^t)}} \right) dz, \quad (12)$$

where $f_{\gamma_j^t}(z)$ denotes the PDF of the received SNR (γ_j^t) at the receiving node j . Due to the complexity of the Q-function, it is challenging to get a closed-form expression for the overall decoding error probability. Thus, using the approximation technique given in [43] and [44], (12) can be approximated as

$$\varepsilon_j^t \approx \int_0^\infty f_{\gamma_j^t}(z) \Theta_j^t(z) dz, \quad (13)$$

where $\Theta_j^t(z)$ denotes the linear approximation of $Q \left(\frac{n_j^t C(\gamma_j^t) - k_j^t}{\sqrt{n_j^t V(\gamma_j^t)}} \right)$ that can be expressed as in [44]

$$\Theta_j^t(z) = \begin{cases} 1, & \gamma_j^t \leq \phi_j^t, \\ \frac{1}{2} - \beta_j^t \sqrt{n_j^t} (\gamma_j^t - \psi_j^t), & \phi_j^t < \gamma_j^t < \delta_j^t, \\ 0, & \gamma_j^t \geq \delta_j^t, \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $\tau_j^t = 2^{\frac{2k_j^t}{n_j^t}}$, $\beta_j^t = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{\tau_j^t-1}}$, $\psi_j^t = 2^{\frac{k_j^t}{n_j^t}} - 1$, $\phi_j^t = \psi_j^t - \frac{1}{2\beta_j^t\sqrt{n_j^t}}$ and $\delta_j^t = \psi_j^t + \frac{1}{2\beta_j^t\sqrt{n_j^t}}$. By using above linear approximation ε_j^t is expressed as

$$\varepsilon_j^t \approx \beta_j^t \sqrt{n_j^t} \int_{\phi_j^t}^{\delta_j^t} F_{\gamma_j^t}(z) dz, \quad (15)$$

where $F_{\gamma_j^t}(z)$ denotes cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the received SNR (γ_j^t) at receiving node j . To calculate error probability at each source i using (10), it is necessary to calculate $\varepsilon_R^{i'}$ and ε_i^R . Using (14) and (15), the BLER at R and each source can be calculated as follows,

$$\varepsilon_R^{i'} \approx \beta_{R'}^{i'} \sqrt{n_{R'}^{i'}} \int_{\phi_{R'}^{i'}}^{\delta_{R'}^{i'}} F_{\gamma_{R'}^{i'}}(z) dz, \quad (16)$$

$$\varepsilon_i^R \approx \beta_i^R \sqrt{n_i^R} \int_{\phi_i^R}^{\delta_i^R} F_{\gamma_i^R}(z) dz, \quad (17)$$

Lemma 1. *An approximation expression for the block error probability at the relay can be derived as*

$$\varepsilon_R^{i'} \approx 1 - \left(\frac{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}\beta_{R'}^{i'}\sqrt{n_{R'}^{i'}}}{\sigma_R^2} \right) \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_{R'}^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} - e^{-\frac{\delta_{R'}^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} \right). \quad (18)$$

Proof. : See Appendix A. \square

Lemma 2. *Block error probability at the opposite receiving node can be derived as follows:*

$$\varepsilon_i^R \approx \beta_i^R \sqrt{n_i^R} \left(\frac{\delta_i^R + \phi_i^R}{2} \right) \sum_{v=1}^V \frac{\pi}{V} \sqrt{1 - \phi_v^2} F_{\gamma_i^R}(q)$$

$$+ R_V), \quad (19)$$

where $\phi_v = \cos\left(\frac{2v-1}{2v}\pi\right)$, $q = \left(\frac{\delta_i^R - \phi_i^R}{2}\right)\phi_v + \left(\frac{\delta_i^R + \phi_i^R}{2}\right)$, V is the complexity-accuracy trade-off factor, while R_V denotes the error term, which is ignored at substantially larger values of V .

Proof. To calculate error probability at S_i , it is necessary to derive the CDF of SNR at the destination node. Using (6), $F_{\gamma_i^R}(z)$ can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\gamma_i^R}(z) &= \mathbb{P}_r\{\gamma_i^R < z\} = 1 - \mathbb{P}_r\{E_R \geq E_{min} \cap \gamma_i^R > z\} \\ F_{\gamma_i^R}(z) &= 1 - \underbrace{\mathbb{P}_r\{E_{min} \leq E_R \leq E_{max} \cap \gamma_i^R > z\}}_{L_1} \\ &\quad - \underbrace{\mathbb{P}_r\{E_R \geq E_{max} \cap \gamma_i^R > z\}}_{L_2}. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Then, substituting $E_R = \rho\eta T_1(P_A\alpha_{AR}g_{AR} + P_B\alpha_{BR}g_{BR})$, L_1 in (20) is evaluated as follows,

$$L_1 = \mathbb{P}_r\{\Omega_1 < I < \Omega_2 \cap Ig_{Ri} > \Omega_3\} \quad (21)$$

or

$$L_1 = \begin{cases} 0, & g_{Ri} < \frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2} \\ \mathbb{P}_r\left\{\frac{\Omega_3}{g_{Ri}} < I \leq \Omega_2\right\}, & \frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2} < g_{Ri} < \frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} \\ \mathbb{P}_r\{\Omega_1 < I \leq \Omega_2\}, & g_{Ri} > \frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

where $\Omega_1 = \frac{E_{min}}{\rho\eta T_1}$, $\Omega_2 = \frac{E_{max}}{\rho\eta T_1}$, $\Omega_3 = \frac{z\sigma_i^2 T_2}{\rho\eta T_1 \alpha_{Ri}}$ and $I = \sum_{i=\{A,B\}} P_i \alpha_{iR} g_{iR}$. To calculate L_1 it is necessary to get PDF and CDF of I and g_{Ri} . Then, to calculate PDF of I , it is considered as summation of two independent random variable as $I = \mu_1 + \mu_2$, where $\mu_1 \sim \exp\left(\frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}}\right)$ and $\mu_2 \sim \exp\left(\frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}}\right)$. Then, using the concepts of convolution of random variables, PDF and CDF of I can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f_I(z) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_{\mu_1}(x)f_{\mu_2}(z-x)dx \\ &= \int_0^z \frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}} e^{-\frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}}x} \frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}} e^{-\frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}}(z-x)} dx, \\ &= \frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}P_B\alpha_{BR}} e^{-\frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}}z} \\ &\quad \int_0^z e^{\left(\frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}} - \frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}}\right)x} dx, \\ f_I(z) &= \begin{cases} \frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR} - P_B\alpha_{BR}} (e^{-\frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}}z} - e^{-\frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}}z}), \\ \text{if } \frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}} \neq \frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}}, \\ \frac{1}{(P_A\alpha_{AR})^2} z e^{-\frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}}z}, & \text{if } \frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}} = \frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}} = \frac{1}{P_A}. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where f denotes PDF function of a random variable. Then, CDF of I can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} F_I(z) &= P(Z \leq z) = \int_0^z f(t)dt \\ F_I(z) &= \begin{cases} 1 + \frac{P_B\alpha_{BR}}{P_A\alpha_{AR} - P_B\alpha_{BR}} e^{-\frac{z}{P_B\alpha_{BR}}} - \frac{P_A\alpha_{AR}}{P_A\alpha_{AR} - P_B\alpha_{BR}} \\ e^{-\frac{z}{P_A\alpha_{AR}}}, & \text{if } P_A\alpha_{AR} \neq P_B\alpha_{BR}, \\ 1 - e^{-\frac{1}{P_A}z} \left(1 + \frac{1}{P_A}z\right), \\ \text{if } \frac{1}{P_A\alpha_{AR}} = \frac{1}{P_B\alpha_{BR}} = \frac{1}{P_A}. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Further, we derive approximations for L_1 as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= \int_{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2}}^{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1}} \left(f_{g_{Ri}}(x) \int_{\frac{\Omega_3}{x}}^{\Omega_2} f_I(y) dy \right) dx + \int_{\Omega_1}^{\Omega_2} f_I(x) dx \\ &\quad \int_{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1}}^{\infty} f_{g_{Ri}}(x) dx, \\ L_1 &= L_3 + (F_I(\Omega_2) - F_I(\Omega_1)) \left(1 - F_{g_{Ri}}\left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1}\right)\right), \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where F denotes CDF function of a random variable and

$$\begin{aligned} L_3 &= \int_{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2}}^{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1}} \left(f_{g_{Ri}}(x) \int_{\frac{\Omega_3}{x}}^{\Omega_2} f_I(y) dy \right) dx \\ &= \int_{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2}}^{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1}} f_{g_{Ri}}(x) \left[F_I(\Omega_2) - F_I\left(\frac{\Omega_3}{x}\right) \right] dx, \\ L_3 &= F_I(\Omega_2) \left[F_{g_{Ri}}\left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1}\right) - F_{g_{Ri}}\left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2}\right) \right] - L_4, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where L_4 can be defined as

$$L_4 = \int_{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2}}^{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1}} f_{g_{Ri}}(x) F_I\left(\frac{\Omega_3}{x}\right) dx. \quad (27)$$

The Gaussian-Chebyshev-Quadrature (GCQ) method [45], [46] is used to obtain a closed-form expression for L_4 since it converges much faster than other approximation methods [47]. Then, (27) can be approximated as follows:

$$L_4 \approx \frac{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} + \frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2}}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\pi}{M} \sqrt{1 - \phi_m^2} f_{g_{Ri}}(z_1) F_I\left(\frac{\Omega_3}{z_1}\right) + R_M, \quad (28)$$

where $\phi_m = \cos\left(\frac{2m-1}{2M}\pi\right)$, $z_1 = \frac{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} - \frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2}}{2} \phi_m + \frac{\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} + \frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2}}{2}$, M is the complexity-accuracy trade-off factor, and R_M is the error term that can be ignored at sufficiently high M values. Finally, closed form expression for L_1 can be approximated as shown in (30). Similarly, L_2 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} L_2 &= \mathbb{P}_r\{I > \Omega_2 \cap g_{Ri} > \Omega_4\}, \\ &= (1 - F_I(\Omega_2)) (1 - F_{g_{Ri}}(\Omega_4)), \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where $\Omega_4 = \frac{z\sigma_i^2 T_2}{E_{max}\alpha_{Ri}}$. Then, CDF of SNR at each destination ($F_{\gamma_i^R}(z)$) can be obtained by substituting (30) and (29) in (20) as in (31). The result can be proved by substituting (31) to (15) and then applying the GCQ method for the integration of the CDF function. \square

Finally, by substituting (18) and (19) into (10) the overall transmission error probability can be calculated.

2) *Transmission Policy 02 : WUC*: Under this policy, the relay waits to transmit updates received from the sources until it harvests the required amount of energy E_{harv} that is defined by the system. The E_{harv} is calculated as $E_{harv} = P_{req}T_2$, where P_{req} is the required power at R for the transmission. In addition, it also assumes that the maximum energy limit that the relay can harvest under this policy is the same as the required energy. As a result, under this policy, transmission power at the relay is fixed to the P_{req} .

Lemma 3. *An approximation for the overall transmission error probability at each source under the WUC policy can be obtained as*

$$\varepsilon_i \approx 1 - \left(\frac{\beta_R^{i'} \beta_i^R \sqrt{n_R^{i'} n_i^R} ((1-\rho) P_{i'} P_{req}) \alpha_{i'} \alpha_{Ri}}{\sigma_R^2 \sigma_i^2} \right) \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_{i'}^R \sigma_R^2}{\alpha_{i'} P_{i'}}} - e^{-\frac{\delta_{i'}^R \sigma_R^2}{\alpha_{iR} (1-\rho) P_{i'}}} \right) \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_i^R \sigma_i^2}{\alpha_{Ri} P_{req}}} - e^{-\frac{\delta_i^R \sigma_i^2}{\alpha_{Ri} P_{req}}} \right). \quad (32)$$

Proof. : See Appendix B. \square

B. Age of Information Analysis

1) *The Age of Information Metric*: Consider a simple communication system containing a source-destination pair. The source sends fresh updates to a network, the network subsequently delivers those updates to the destination. The generation time of the most recent update received by the destination at timestamp t denotes as $u(t)$. Then, the AoI can be then described as a random process as follows:

$$\Delta(t) = t - u(t). \quad (33)$$

As illustrated in the Fig.2, it is assumed that at $t = 0$, the measurement of AoI starts. The AoI at the opposite source is set to $\Delta(0) = \Delta_0$. The source generates updates at time instant $u_0, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n$. These updates pass through the relay and the destination receive these updates at time instant $z_0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n$. As illustrated in Fig. 2, data update k is transmitted from the source at time instant $t = u_k$ and it is successfully delivered to the opposite source at time

instant $z_k = u_k + Y_k$. Therefore, the AoI at the destination can be calculated as $\Delta(z_k) = z_k - u_k$. The AoI grows at unit rate until the next update is delivered to the destination. Similarly, AoI just before the $i + 1$ update is successfully delivered and can be written as $\Delta(z_{i+1}^-) = Y_i + X_i$. Then, after the update is delivered, the AoI drops as $\Delta(z_{i+1}^+) = Y_{i+1}$. Hence, the age process $\Delta(t)$ exhibits the saw-tooth pattern as illustrated in Fig. 2. For a given time period, time average AoI can be computed using the area under $\Delta(t)$. For this system, the observation time interval considered as $[0, T_{int}]$ and $N(T_{int}) = \max\{n \mid u_n \leq T_{int}\}$ denotes the number of updates by time T_{int} . The area under the curve can be treated as a sum of the polygon area P_0 , the trapezoidal areas Q_i for $1 \leq i \leq N(T_{int})$ (Q_1 and Q_n are highlighted in the figure) and the triangular area P_1 of width Y_n over the time interval (u_n, z_n) as shown in Fig. 2. Then, the time average age can be calculated by applying graphical methods to saw-tooth age waveform as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{T_{int}} &= \frac{1}{T_{int}} \int_0^{T_{int}} \Delta(t) dt \\ &= \frac{P_0 + P_1 + \sum_{i=1}^{N(T_{int})} Q_i}{T_{int}}, \quad (34) \\ &= \frac{P_0 + P_1}{T_{int}} + \frac{N(T_{int})}{T_{int}} \frac{1}{N(T_{int})} \sum_{i=1}^{N(T_{int})} Q_i, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$Q_i = \frac{1}{2} (X_i + Y_{i+1})^2 - \frac{1}{2} Y_{i+1}^2 = Y_{i+1} X_i + \frac{1}{2} X_i^2,$$

where X is the inter-arrival time between delivered updates and Y is the system time of such an update. In here, it is assumed that system is stationary and ergodic [48], the time average age $\Delta_{T_{int}}$ tends to ensemble-average age when $T_{int} \rightarrow \infty$, i.e.

$$\Delta_{AAOI} = \lim_{T_{int} \rightarrow \infty} \Delta_T. \quad (35)$$

When $T_{int} \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{N(T_{int})}{T_{int}} \rightarrow \frac{1}{\mathbb{E}[X]}$, $\frac{1}{N(T_{int})} \sum_{i=1}^{N(T_{int})} Q_i \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[Q]$ and $\frac{P_0 + P_1}{T}$ term goes to zero. Thus, the AAOI can be written as

$$\Delta_{AAOI} = \frac{\frac{\mathbb{E}[X^2]}{2} + \mathbb{E}[XY]}{\mathbb{E}[X]}. \quad (36)$$

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 \approx F_I(\Omega_2) \left[F_{g_{Ri}} \left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} \right) - F_{g_{Ri}} \left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2} \right) \right] - \frac{\Omega_3 + \Omega_2}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sqrt{1 - \phi_m^2} f_{g_{Ri}}(z_1) F_I \left(\frac{\Omega_3}{z_1} \right) + R_M \\ + (F_I(\Omega_2) - F_I(\Omega_1)) \left(1 - F_{g_{Ri}} \left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} \right) \right). \quad (30) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\gamma_i^R}(z) \approx 1 - F_I(\Omega_2) \left[F_{g_{Ri}} \left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} \right) - F_{g_{Ri}} \left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_2} \right) \right] - \frac{\Omega_3 + \Omega_2}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sqrt{1 - \phi_m^2} f_{g_{Ri}}(z_1) F_I \left(\frac{\Omega_3}{z_1} \right) \\ + R_M + (F_I(\Omega_2) - F_I(\Omega_1)) \left(1 - F_{g_{Ri}} \left(\frac{\Omega_3}{\Omega_1} \right) \right) - (1 - F_I(\Omega_2)) (1 - F_{g_{Ri}}(\Omega_4)). \quad (31) \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 2. Evolution of AoI $\Delta(t)$ with the time at the destination in a simple commutation system containing a source and destination pair:: Each source generate updates at time stamps $u_0, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n$ and the opposite source receive these updates at time stamps $z_0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n$.

2) *Transmission Policy 01 : TWW* : This section calculates the AAOI of the two-way relay system. The S_A and S_B generate new status updates every transmission circle to keep the information at the corresponding destinations as fresh as possible. Then, generated updates are transmitted to its opposite source using relay system. If the generation time of the freshest update received at opposite source time stamp t is $g(t)$, then AoI can be defined as a random process as

$$\Delta(t) = t - g(t). \quad (37)$$

As illustrated in Fig.3, it is assumed that at $t = 0$ the measurements of the AoI starts and the AoI at the opposite source (destination) is set to $\Delta(0) = \Delta_0$. Each source generates updates at time stamps g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{n-1} and the opposite source receive these updates at time stamps g_2, g_3, \dots, g_n . As

illustrated in Fig.3, data update i is transmitted from the source at time stamp $t = g_i$ and it is successfully delivered to the its opposite source at time stamp $g_{i+1} = g_i + T$ where T is total time allocated for a transmission circle and $T = T_1 + T_2$. Therefore, if update packet delivered successfully, at the time g_{i+1} , the AoI at the opposite source can be calculated as

$$\Delta(g_{i+1}) = T. \quad (38)$$

The AoI increases linearly until the next update is successfully delivered to the opposite source. As an example, since one packet fails to be decoded at time g_3 , $\Delta(t)$ continues to increase linearly. Here, X_i is the inter departure time between two consecutive successfully received status updates at S_i and it is a geometric random variable with mean $E[X_i] = \frac{T}{1-\varepsilon_i}$ and second moment $E[X_i^2] = \frac{T^2(1+\varepsilon_i)}{(1-\varepsilon_i)^2}$. It assumes that the end-

Fig. 3. Evolution of AoI $\Delta(t)$ at opposite source (destination) with the time under the TWW policy: Each source generate updates at time stamps g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{n-1} and the opposite source receive these updates at time stamps g_2, g_3, \dots, g_n .

to-end delay of each successfully received update is always a constant given by $E[Y_i] = T_1 + T_2 = T$. Then, applying graphical methods to saw-tooth age waveform in Fig.3 and using (36), AAoI at each $S_i, i \in (A, B)$ is computed as follows:

$$\Delta_i^{AAoI} = \frac{E[X_i^2]}{2E[X_i]} + T, \quad (39)$$

Lemma 4. For the two way relay network, the expression of the AAoI at each source can be obtained as follows:

$$\Delta_i^{AAoI} = \frac{T}{2} + \frac{T}{1 - \varepsilon_i} \quad (40)$$

Proof. The result can be proved by substituting $E[X_i] = \frac{T}{1 - \varepsilon_i}$ and $E[X_i^2] = \frac{T^2(1 + \varepsilon_i)}{(1 - \varepsilon_i)^2}$ into (39). \square

The expected weighted sum AAoI of the two-way relay system can be calculated as follows,

$$\Delta_{Sum}^{AAoI} = \sum_{i \in \{A, B\}} \omega_i \Delta_i^{AAoI} \quad (41)$$

where ω_i is the weighting coefficient at S_i .

3) *Transmission Policy 02 : WUC :* Under this policy, the delay induced by the energy collecting time to harvest the required energy has a significant impact on the AoI. This time period is determined by two factors: the amount of energy necessary for the transmission at the relay and the randomness of harvested energy in each time slot. As a result, the important issue is how long it takes to collect the amount of energy required for the transmission. Under this condition, the end-to-end delay time is not a constant as it was previously, and it can be defined as the sum of the waiting and receiving time at the relay T_w and the transmission time between R and the opposite source T_2 . The number of time slots in T_w is defined as m_w (one time slot is equal to T_1 amount of time). The probability mass function (PMF) of the m_w defined as $P_w(m)$ gives the probability that m_w is exactly equal to m number of time slots. Then, $P_w(m)$ obtained as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} P_w(m) &= \mathbb{P}_r \left\{ \left(\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} E_R^k < E_{harv} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \cap \left(\sum_{k=1}^m E_R^k \geq E_{harv} \right) \right\} \\ &= \mathbb{P}_r \left\{ \left(\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \sum_{i \in \{A, B\}} \rho \eta P_i G_{iR}^k T_1 < E_{harv} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \cap \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{i \in \{A, B\}} \rho \eta P_i G_{iR}^k T_1 \geq E_{harv} \right) \right\} \\ &= \mathbb{P}_r \left\{ \left(\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \sum_{i \in \{A, B\}} P_i G_{iR}^k < E'_{harv} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \cap \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{i \in \{A, B\}} P_i G_{iR}^k \geq E'_{harv} \right) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \mathbb{P}_r \left\{ \left(\sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \sum_{i \in \{A, B\}} P_i \alpha_{iR} G_{iR}^k < E'_{harv} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. \cap \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{i \in \{A, B\}} P_i \alpha_{iR} G_{iR}^k \geq E'_{harv} \right) \right\} \\ &= \mathbb{P}_r \{ (Z < E'_{harv}) \cap (Z + V \geq E'_{harv}) \} \\ &= \int_{z=0}^{E'_{harv}} \int_{v=E'_{harv}-z}^{\infty} f_Z(z) f_V(v) dv dz \\ P_w(m) &= \int_{z=0}^{E'_{harv}} f_Z(z) [1 - F_V(E'_{harv} - z)] dz \end{aligned}$$

where $E'_{harv} = \frac{E_{harv}}{\rho \eta T_1}$, Z and V are random variables. The distribution of the Z is the same as the mixture of two mutually independent Erlang distributions. It is known as hyper-Erlang distribution [49], [50]. Therefore, the PDF of Z is given by

$$\begin{aligned} f_Z(z) &= \frac{(-1)^{m-1} \xi_A^{m-1} \xi_B^{m-1}}{(\xi_B - \xi_A)^{2(m-1)}} \left[e^{-\xi_A z} \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \binom{2m-k-3}{m-2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{(\xi_A - \xi_B)^k z^{k-1}}{(k-1)!} + e^{-\xi_B z} \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \binom{2m-k-3}{m-2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{(\xi_B - \xi_A)^k z^{k-1}}{(k-1)!} \right], \quad (42) \end{aligned}$$

where $\xi_A = \frac{1}{P_A \alpha_{AR}}$, $\xi_B = \frac{1}{P_B \alpha_{BR}}$ and $\xi_A \neq \xi_B$ and

$$F_V(t) = \mathbb{P}(V \leq t) = 1 + \frac{\xi_A}{\xi_B - \xi_A} e^{-\xi_B t} - \frac{\xi_B}{\xi_B - \xi_A} e^{-\xi_A t}. \quad (43)$$

When $\xi_A \neq \xi_B$, it is challenging to find closed-form expression for $P_w(m)$. However, when $\xi_A = \xi_B = \xi$, we have

$$f_Z(z) = \frac{\xi^{2m-2} e^{-\xi z} z^{2m-3}}{(2m-3)!} \sim \text{Erlang}(2m-2, \xi), \quad (44)$$

$$F_V(t) = \mathbb{P}(V \leq t) = 1 - e^{-\xi t} [1 + \xi t], \quad (45)$$

$$P_w(m) = \frac{e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} (\xi E'_{harv})^{2m-2} [2m-1 + \xi E'_{harv}]}{(2m-1)!}. \quad (46)$$

To compare the two transmission policies we consider that $\xi_A = \xi_B = \xi$.

Lemma 5. The first and second moments of the number of slots in the sum of the waiting and receiving time at the relay are computed as follows,

$$E[m_w] = 1 + \frac{\xi E'_{harv}}{2}, \quad (47)$$

$$E[m_w^2] = 1 + \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^2}{4} + \frac{5\xi E'_{harv}}{4}, \quad (48)$$

Proof. : See Appendix C. \square

Then, the first and second moments of waiting time are calculated as follows,

$$E[T_w] = \left(1 + \frac{\xi E'_{harv}}{2} \right) T_1, \quad (49)$$

$$E [T_w^2] = \left(1 + \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^2}{4} + \frac{5\xi E'_{harv}}{4} \right) T_1^2. \quad (50)$$

Lemma 6. *The AAOI at each source in a decode and forward two-way relay network under the WUC policy can be derived as*

$$\Delta_i^{AAOI} = \frac{(1 + \varepsilon_i) (T_2^2 + 2T_2 E [T_w] + E [T_w^2])}{2(1 - \varepsilon_i) (E [T_w] + 2T_2) + T_2 + E [T_w]}. \quad (51)$$

Proof. To calculate AAOI at each source, it is necessary to calculate the overall transmission error probability ε_i at each source. It is assumed that after one successful update received at the opposite source, n_f number of failures occur until the next successful update received where n_f is geometrically distributed with parameter $1 - \varepsilon_i$. The time span between two consecutive successful updates reception is $X = (n_f + 1)Y$, where $Y = T_w + T_2$ denotes the time incurred to traverse through the network. Thus, X is distributed as

$$X \sim \sum_{n_f=0}^{\infty} (\varepsilon_i)^{n_f} (1 - \varepsilon_i) \delta (X - (n_f + 1)Y), \quad (52)$$

where $\delta (X)$ refers to the dirac impulse [51]. The AAOI stated in (36) depends on Y and first and second moments of the X . Thus, $E[X]$ can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} E[X] &= \sum_{n_f=0}^{\infty} (\varepsilon_i)^{n_f} (1 - \varepsilon_i) (n_f + 1) E[Y], \\ &= \frac{E[Y]}{1 - \varepsilon_i} = \frac{E[T_w] + T_2}{1 - \varepsilon_i}, \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

and the second-order-moment $E[X^2]$ can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} E[X^2] &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} E \left[((n+1)Y)^2 (\varepsilon_i)^n (1 - \varepsilon_i) (n+1) \right], \\ &= E[Y^2] \frac{1 + \varepsilon_i}{(1 - \varepsilon_i)^2}, \\ E[X^2] &= \frac{1 + \varepsilon_i}{(1 - \varepsilon_i)^2} [T_2^2 + 2T_2 E [T_w] + E [T_w^2]]. \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

Then, using (36), Δ_i^{AAOI} under WUC policy is formulated as follows,

$$\Delta_i^{AAOI} = \frac{E[X^2]}{2E[X]} + T_2 + \frac{E[T_w X]}{E[X]}, \quad (55)$$

and assuming T_w and X are independent and identically distributed random variables, AAOI is given by (55) can be re-formulated as

$$\Delta_i^{AAOI} = \frac{E[X^2]}{2E[X]} + T_2 + E[T_w]. \quad (56)$$

Then, the result can be proved by substituting (53) and (54) into (56). \square

The expected weighted sum AAOI of the two-way relay system under WUC policy can be calculate using (41).

III. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we present the analytical and simulation results. Unless mentioned, the simulation parameters are listed in Table I.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS [52], [53]

Parameter	Value
Distance between S_A and R (d_{AR})	30 m
Distance between S_B and R (d_{BR})	30 m
Carrier frequency (f_c)	900 MHz
Speed of the light (m/s) (c)	$3 \times 10^8 \text{ms}^{-1}$
Transmission power at S_A (P_A)	1 W
Transmission power at S_B (P_B)	1 W
Symbol duration (T_s)	20 μs
n_R^A, n_R^B	200 bits
n_A^R, n_B^R	200 bits
k_R^A, k_R^B	32 bits
Noise power ($\sigma_R^2, \sigma_A^2, \sigma_B^2$)	-100 dBm
E_{max}	0.001 J
P_{min}	0.0001 mW
P_{req}	0.01 mW
Power spitting factor (ρ)	0.5
ω_A	0.5
ω_B	0.5
Energy conversion efficiency (η)	0.9

Fig. 4. BLER as a function of transmission power.

Fig.4 presents the comparison of BLER performance between MC-based simulations and theoretical approximations for both transmissions and EH policies. Theoretical BLER closely matches simulation outcomes for both policies. In the context of the TWW policy, it is observed that the BLER nearly reaches 1 when the transmission power of the sources is low. This is due to the fact that, under the TWW policy, the relay does not wait to harvest enough energy for transmission, and energy harvesting depends solely on the power transmitted during the first transmission slot. Consequently, with low transmission power from the source, the energy available for harvesting remains insufficient. As a result, the received

SNR at the receiver is very low, leading to a high level of BLER. In contrast, increasing the transmission power of the sources enhances the energy harvesting capacity of the relay, consequently allowing for the maintenance of a substantial level of transmission power at the relay. As a result, this leads to a reduction in BLER when the transmission power of sources increases. Conversely, BLER under the WUC policy remains relatively stable despite changes in the transmission power of the sources. The WUC policy allows the relay to wait for sufficient power before transmitting, maintaining a nearly constant relay transmission power. As a result, it maintains a high received SNR at the receiver, leading to a low level of BLER. Hence, variations in the transmission power of the sources have a minimal impact on BLER, making the WUC policy more suited for applications requiring a high level of reliability.

Fig. 5. Weighed sum AAoI as a function of transmission power.

In Fig.5, the weighted sum of AAoI is plotted as a function of transmission power at the sources. Under both policies, as the transmit power at the sources increases, the weighted sum of AAoI decreases. However, the decrease in the weighted sum of AAoI is more pronounced under the WUC policy when power increases. This is due to, as per Lemma 6, the AAoI under the WUC policy depending on the transmission waiting time T_w and the BLER at the receiving end. Additionally, according to Lemma 5, increasing transmission power at the source leads to a reduction in both T_w and BLER. As a result, increasing transmission power leads to a reduction in the weighted sum of AAoI, especially due to the high influence of waiting time reduction. On the other hand, as per Lemma 4, under the TWW policy, if transmission time is fixed, only BLER becomes a main factor influencing the weighted sum of AAoI. From this figure, we can conclude that, especially under low-level transmission power, the influence of T_w is more significant than BLER on the weighted sum of AAoI. Thus, the TWW policy maintains a low level of the weighted sum of

AAoI when transmission power is low compared to the WUC policy. Consequently, the TWW policy emerges as a suitable choice for low-powered IoT applications with stringent requirements for information freshness. On the other hand, the WUC policy proves more suitable for applications where reliability takes precedence over information freshness. These findings highlight the significance of selecting an appropriate policy based on the specific requirements of the application, ensuring optimal performance.

Fig. 6. Weighed sum AAoI as a function of transmission power under varying fading factors.

The weighted sum of AAoI is plotted against transmission power under varying channel conditions, including Rician and Rayleigh fading, with different fading factors (K_f) for Rician fading in Fig. 6. The figure demonstrates that, under the TWW policy, line-of-sight channel conditions significantly affect the performance of the system. Under the TWW policy, there are challenges in maintaining an adequate SNR at the receiver due to low transmission power at the relay, thus underscoring the critical role of channel conditions. Consequently, a large Rician factor aids in maintaining a low BLER, ensuring better information freshness as depicted in the figure, compared to non-line-of-sight fading conditions such as Rayleigh fading. Conversely, under the WUC policy, changes in the fading factor have a negligible impact on AAoI. This outcome is due to the transmission strategy of the WUC policy, which allows the relay to transmit after it has accumulated sufficient energy, thereby ensuring a high level of received SNR at the receiver. Consequently, the impact of fading is significantly reduced in the WUC policy owing to the higher transmission power at the relay compared to that of the TWW policy.

In Fig. 7, the relationship between the weighted sum of the AAoI and block length for both policies is illustrated. When the transmission power is high, there is a noticeable increase in AAoI as the block length is increased for both policies. Typically, an increase in the block length leads to a decrease in BLER [15] and an extension of transmission

Fig. 7. Weighed sum AAoI as a function of block-length.

time. Lemmas 4 and 6 indicate that a reduction in BLER should decrease AAoI, while also suggesting that prolonged transmission time contributes to an increase in AAoI. Notably, in scenarios with high transmission power, the impact of the extended transmission time becomes more pronounced than the reduction in BLER on AAoI. Thus, under high transmission power conditions, increasing the block length results in a rise in the weighted sum of AAoI for both policies. Under the TWW policy, when the transmission power is low, increasing the block length from a small value reduces BLER [15]. Consequently, the AAoI decreases according to Lemma 4 until it reaches its optimal value. In this scenario, the decrease in BLER has a more significant impact on AAoI compared to the increase in transmission time. However, once the block length surpasses its optimal value, increasing it further only serves to extend the transmission time. Consequently, AAoI starts to increase, especially in high-power scenarios. However, for the WUC policy, under all transmission power scenarios, increasing the block length always increases the AAoI since it maintains a higher received SNR level at the destination using constant transmission power in the relay node. Hence, in the figure, we observe that beyond a block length of 200, under all transmission power scenarios, AAoI exhibits the same behavior. Furthermore, the gap between the AAoI under the two policies decreases as the power level increases. This is due to increasing block length, which increases both transmission time and waiting time. Both parameters affect AAoI under the WUC policy, while under the TWW policy, only an increase in transmission time affects AAoI.

Additionally, concerning the WUC policy, numerical results closely match the approximated outcomes. However, in the low SNR regime for the TWW policy, the approximated AAoI results do not align well with the numerically simulated results. This discrepancy arises because the approximations in equations (18) and (19) are accurate for moderate SNR values [7]. Moreover, this inconsistency is particularly evident when the block length is lower than 200, as finite block length

information theory-based approximations fail to reconcile with simulation-based results, especially under low SNR scenarios.

Fig. 8. Weighed sum AAoI as a function of update size

In Fig. 8, the weighted sum of AAoI is presented as a function of the update size for both policies. Under low transmission power conditions, if the packet size increases, the AAoI also increases under the TWW policy, while there is no significant change under the WUC policy. This is due to the fact that under the TWW policy, due to low transmission power at the relay, varying update sizes under a fixed block length increase BLER, which affects the AAoI as in Lemma 4. However, under the WUC policy, transmission power at the relay is maintained at a satisfactory level, resulting in a low BLER. Additionally, there are no changes in the transmission time or waiting time since the block length is fixed. Consequently, the AAoI under the WUC policy remains relatively unchanged when the block length varies. In a high transmission power scenario, the packet size does not have a significant impact on the AAoI for either policy. This is due to the fact that with high SNR, the BLER is very small, and increasing the update size results in a slight increase in BLER [15]. However, the effect of this small variation in BLER does not significantly affect the AAoI since other parameters such as waiting time and transmission time are also fixed. Furthermore, it has been observed that the TWW policy outperforms the WUC policy in terms of information freshness under low SNR scenarios for all packet sizes.

Fig. 9 illustrates the weighted sum AAoI as a function of the distance between the relay and sources, where both sources are located at the same distance from the relay (i.e., $d_{BR} = d_{AR}$). The AAoI grows as the distance between the sources and the relay increases (i.e., the SNR drops). This is due to the fact that decreasing the SNR increases BLER, as well as the waiting time for harvesting under the WUC policy, thereby increasing AAoI according to Lemma 4 and 6. Additionally, when the distance is increased, it increases AAoI under the TWW policy dramatically compared to the linear growth under the WUC policy. This is due to the fact

Fig. 9. Weighed sum AAOI as a function of distance.

that under the TWW policy, increments in distance increase BLER significantly due to low transmission power at the relay. Moreover, the approximated results coincide with the numerically simulated results under the WUC policy, even for long distances. However, concerning the TWW policy, as the distance increases, there is a significant deviation between the approximated and simulated results. This discrepancy is particularly noticeable for low SNR values, where the approximation used (13) does not perform as effectively for low SNR values [44]. Overall, the WUC policy outperforms the TWW policy for long-distance communication since it maintains better freshness of the information at the receiving node, whereas the TWW policy maintains a very high level of AAOI for long distances.

 Fig. 10. Weighed sum AAOI as a function of P_{req} under WUC policy.

Fig. 10 shows the weighed sum AAOI as a function of P_{req} under the WUC policy. This figure reveals that there is an

optimal value for P_{req} . The system exhibits a larger AAOI for small P_{req} values, as this increases the BLER at the receiving node. In such circumstances, the impact of the higher BLER at the opposing receiving source on AAOI becomes more significant than the short waiting time required to harvest small P_{req} values. Conversely, increasing P_{req} from a low value to an optimal value reduces the AAOI, thanks to the reduction in BLER resulting from the higher transmission power. In this scenario, the benefit of a small BLER is more significant than the increased waiting time for harvesting. However, beyond the optimal value, the impact of waiting time for harvesting outweighs the benefits of reduced decoding error. Thus, it can be observed from the figure that increasing P_{req} above its optimal value rapidly increases the AAOI of the system. Additionally, for small P_{req} values, the approximate AAOI deviates from the simulated value, where the approximation used in equation (13) does not perform as effectively for low SNR values [44]. In summary, maintaining an optimal P_{req} is essential to achieve a better AAOI under WUC policy.

 Fig. 11. Weighed sum AAOI as a function of P_{min} under TWW policy .

Fig. 11 illustrates the weighed sum AAOI as a function of P_{min} under the TWW policy. It is observed that the weighed sum AAOI of the system monotonically increases with P_{min} , since high P_{min} threshold values increase update loss at the relay. This causes an increase in AAOI due to infrequent updates at the receiving node. This emphasizes the importance of the relay being equipped with more efficient communication devices. Based on the simulation results, the following key observations can be identified:

- The WUC policy is the optimal choice for applications with high-reliability requirements, prioritizing reliability over information freshness. On the other hand, the TWW policy is the preferred option for applications focused on achieving better information freshness conditions.
- Under high SNR conditions, a short block length consistently maintains the freshness of information. However, increasing the block length leads to an increase in AAOI. In contrast, in the low SNR regime, short block lengths can increase AAOI due to the higher frequency of erroneous updates, particularly under the TWW policy.

Thus, short block-length communication does not always contribute to maintaining freshness, even though it helps in achieving low latency.

- In high SNR conditions, the update size has minimal impact on AAoI for both policies. However, in low SNR conditions, AAoI increases with the update size, especially under the TWW policy. Therefore, considering the update size is crucial when designing a wireless communication system following the TWW policy.
- For applications with a large distance between the relay and the sources, the WUC policy is the ideal choice. On the other hand, the TWW policy is more suitable for short-distance applications.
- There exists a sub-optimal value of P_{req} in terms of minimizing AAoI. This is primarily due to lower P_{req} reducing the time required for energy harvesting, while simultaneously increasing the probability of decoding errors.

These observations provide valuable insights into the performance and trade-offs of different policies under varying SNR, block length, update size, and distance conditions.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper estimated the freshness of information in a SWIPT-assisted short-packet two-way relaying wireless communication system for mission-critical applications. We have considered two types of transmission policies at the relay, namely, TWW and WUC. Approximations were derived for the weighted sum of AAoI of the relay system for both policies. Furthermore, we studied the effect of various factors on the weighted sum AAoI of the proposed system, including transmission power, packet size, the distance between the relay and sources and block-length. Moreover, it was observed that short block lengths support maintaining the freshness of the information only when the SNR is high. In addition, it is noticed that the ‘‘TWW’’ policy outperforms in terms of AAoI while ‘‘WUC’’ policy is best suited when the wireless communication application requires higher reliability. Furthermore, we discovered that packet size under fixed block-length does not influence data freshness in the high SNR regime. However, short packet communication support maintaining a better AoI in the low SNR regime under fixed block-length. Considering all the numerical simulation results, it is proven that ‘‘WUC’’ is the optimal transmission policy for applications with high-reliability requirements, while ‘‘TWW’’ is best for applications with high information freshness requirements. In the future, we will deploy a small-scale prototype to compare the effectiveness of these transmission policies in a more realistic environment.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF LEMMA 1

The PDF of SNR at relay from each source can be calculated using (3) as follows,

$$f_{\gamma_R^{i'}}(x) = \frac{\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}} e^{-\frac{x\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} \quad (57)$$

Then, the CDF is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\gamma_R^{i'}}(z) &= \mathbb{P}_r(\gamma_R^{i'} \leq z) = \int_{-\infty}^z f_{\gamma_R^{i'}}(t) dt \\ &= 1 - e^{-\frac{z\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}}. \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

From (16) block error probability at the relay is calculated as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_R^{i'} &\approx \beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}} \int_{\phi_R^{i'}}^{\delta_R^{i'}} F_{\gamma_R^{i'}}(z) dz \\ &\approx \beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}} \int_{\phi_R^{i'}}^{\delta_R^{i'}} 1 - e^{-\frac{z\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} dz, \\ &\approx \beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}} \left((\delta_R^{i'} - \phi_R^{i'}) - \int_{\phi_R^{i'}}^{\delta_R^{i'}} e^{-\frac{z\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} dz \right), \\ &\approx \beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}} \left(\psi_R^{i'} + \frac{1}{2\beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}}} - \left(\psi_R^{i'} - \frac{1}{2\beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}}} \right) \right) \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}\beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}}}{\sigma_R^2} \right) \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_R^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - e^{-\frac{\delta_R^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} \right), \\ \varepsilon_R^{i'} &\approx 1 - \left(\frac{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}\beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}}}{\sigma_R^2} \right) \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_R^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - e^{-\frac{\delta_R^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

APPENDIX B PROOF OF LEMMA 3

The system overall transmission error probability (ε_i) at each source can be calculated using (10) and $\varepsilon_R^{i'}$ and ε_i^R can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_R^{i'} &\approx 1 - \left(\frac{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}\beta_R^{i'} \sqrt{n_R^{i'}}}{\sigma_R^2} \right) \\ &\quad \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_R^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} - e^{-\frac{\delta_R^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} \right), \\ \varepsilon_i^R &\approx 1 - \left(\frac{P_{req}\alpha_{Ri}\beta_i^R \sqrt{n_i^R}}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_i^R\sigma_i^2}{P_{req}\alpha_{Ri}}} - e^{-\frac{\delta_i^R\sigma_i^2}{P_{req}\alpha_{Ri}}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

Then, using equation (10), ε_i is calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_i &= \varepsilon_R^{i'} + (1 - \varepsilon_R^{i'}) \varepsilon_i^R \\ \varepsilon_i &\approx 1 - \left(\frac{\beta_R^{i'}\beta_i^R \sqrt{n_R^{i'}n_i^R}((1-\rho)P_{i'}P_{req})\alpha_{i'R}\alpha_{Ri}}{\sigma_R^2\sigma_i^2} \right) \\ &\quad \times \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_R^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} - e^{-\frac{\delta_R^{i'}\sigma_R^2}{(1-\rho)P_{i'}\alpha_{i'R}}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (62a)$$

$$\times \left(e^{-\frac{\phi_i^R \sigma_i^2}{P_{\text{req}} \alpha R_i}} - e^{-\frac{\delta_i^R \sigma_i^2}{P_{\text{req}} \alpha R_i}} \right) \quad (62b)$$

APPENDIX C
PROOF OF LEMMA 5

By using the PMF given in (46), the first moments of m_w is computed as follows:

$$E[m_w] = e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^{2m-2} \left[2m-1 + \xi E'_{harv} \right]}{(2m-1)!}, \quad (63a)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{m (\xi E'_{harv})^{2m-2}}{(2m-2)!} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{m (\xi E'_{harv})^{2m-1}}{(2m-1)!} \right), \quad (63b)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(\sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{(T+1) (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T}}{(2T)!} + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{(T+1) (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T+1}}{(2T+1)!} \right), \quad (63c)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(\sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^{2T}}{(2T)!} + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^{2T+1}}{(2T+1)!} + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{T (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T}}{(2T)!} + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{T (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T+1}}{(2T+1)!} \right), \quad (63d)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(\cosh(\xi E'_{harv}) + \sinh(\xi E'_{harv}) + \frac{\sinh(\xi E'_{harv}) \xi E'_{harv}}{2} + \frac{\cosh(\xi E'_{harv}) \xi E'_{harv}}{2} \right), \quad (63e)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(e^{\xi E'_{harv}} + \frac{e^{\xi E'_{harv}} \xi E'_{harv}}{2} \right) \quad (63f)$$

$$E[m_w] = 1 + \frac{\xi E'_{harv}}{2}. \quad (63g)$$

Then, second moments of m_w is computed as follows:

$$E[m_w^2] = e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{m^2 (\xi E'_{harv})^{2m-2} \left[2m-1 + \xi E'_{harv} \right]}{(2m-1)!}, \quad (64a)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{m^2 (\xi E'_{harv})^{2m-2}}{(2m-2)!} + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{m^2 (\xi E'_{harv})^{2m-1}}{(2m-1)!} \right), \quad (64b)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(\sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{(T+1)^2 (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T}}{(2T)!} + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{(T+1)^2 (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T+1}}{(2T+1)!} \right), \quad (64c)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(\sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^{2T}}{(2T)!} + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^{2T+1}}{(2T+1)!} + 2 \left(\sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{T (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T}}{(2T)!} + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{T (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T+1}}{(2T+1)!} \right) + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{T^2 (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T}}{(2T)!} + \sum_{T=0}^{\infty} \frac{T^2 (\xi E'_{harv})^{2T+1}}{(2T+1)!} \right), \quad (64d)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(\cosh(\xi E'_{harv}) + \sinh(\xi E'_{harv}) + \sinh(\xi E'_{harv}) \xi E'_{harv} + \cosh(\xi E'_{harv}) \xi E'_{harv} + \frac{\xi E'_{harv} (\sinh(\xi E'_{harv}) + \xi E'_{harv} \cosh(\xi E'_{harv}))}{4} + \frac{\xi E'_{harv} (\cosh(\xi E'_{harv}) + \xi E'_{harv} \sinh(\xi E'_{harv}))}{4} \right), \quad (64e)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} + e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \xi E'_{harv} + \frac{\xi E'_{harv} (e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} + e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \xi E'_{harv})}{4} \right), \quad (64f)$$

$$= e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \left(e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} + \frac{5e^{-\xi E'_{harv}} \xi E'_{harv}}{4} + \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^2 (e^{-\xi E'_{harv}})}{4} \right), \quad (64g)$$

$$E[m_w^2] = 1 + \frac{(\xi E'_{harv})^2}{4} + \frac{5\xi E'_{harv}}{4}. \quad (64h)$$

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